

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D2.4

1st Mapping of Needs report

WP 2 – T2.1

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¹ PU = Public

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Abstract

In order to best achieve the objectives of PARC and address regulatory/policy needs at EU and/or National level, Task 2.1 “Priority setting”, in charge of coordinating the prioritisation process under PARC, mapped the needs identified by PARC’s Governing Board members with regards to human and environmental exposure to chemicals resulting in health impacts. The mapping of needs focused on the second part of the partnership, i.e. years 4 to 7 and mainly concerned the three PARC Workpackages involved in Research and Innovation activities, WPs 4-5-6. The suggested priorities and needs were then compiled and are currently being discussed among the Management Board and PARC partners. Workshops are foreseen to screen the most relevant ones while taking into account their feasibility. Other consultations will also take place to best refine and rank the needs. Subsequently, PARC’s list of priorities will be defined. Micro and nano plastics and micro and nano particles, the most frequently designated group of substances in the survey, will be dealt with separately, as questions have been raised about PARC’s capacity to address them. The Management Board decided to nominate Chemical Leaders for these groups, and then evaluate their inclusion in PARC. Another ‘mapping of needs’ round will take place at the end of the partnership to identify PARC’s legacy.

Key Words

New priorities, Prioritisation round, Policy need, Regulatory need, Mapping of Needs

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Acronyms

AOP: Adverse Outcome Pathway

AWP: Annual Work Plan

CL: Chemical Leader

CLP Regulation: Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulation

CT: Coordination Team

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

EEA: European Environmental Agency

EFSA: European Food Safety Authority

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

FGD: Focus Group Discussion

GB PR: Governing Board Principal Representatives

GB: Governing Board

HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring for EU

IATAs: Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment

IB: International Board

KARC: Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge

MB: Management Board

NH: National Hub

PMs: Project Managers
RRM: Rapid Response Report
SF: Stakeholder Forum
TL: Task Leader
WP: Workpackage
WPL: Workpackage Leader

1. Introduction

PARC's partnership planned to conduct three prioritisation rounds over its lifetime, i.e. May 2022-April 2029. The first round took place before the launch of the partnership, the second round started in 2023, and the third round will occur at the end to define the legacy. In fact, Task 2.1 is responsible of mapping the needs, prioritising the activities (based on specific criteria) and, preparing the Background Documents¹. The first prioritisation was a result of the third prioritisation round done under HBM4EU and a survey sent to PARC's interim Governing Board (GB) members. The outcomes were discussed, prioritised and translated into projects proposal, integrated in the Annual Work plans (AWP) of the first half of the partnership (i.e. years 1 to 3). The prioritisation criteria for substances or methods were presented in the deliverable D2.1 "Prioritisation Criteria Report". The second prioritisation round started in 2023 by mapping the needs for the second half of the partnership, i.e. years 4 to 7 (2025-2029). The Mapping of Needs done under this second prioritisation round is described in this deliverable.

2. Methods

After the first prioritisation round, and before embarking on the second, the Coordination Team (CT) gathered feedback from the Workpackage Leaders (WPLs), Task Leaders (TLs) and Project Managers (PMs) on their experiences, during the first prioritisation round, through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) that took place on the 3rd, 5th and 9th of May 2023. Each FGD lasted 90 minutes, WPLs/TLs and PMs from Workpackages (WPs) 4, 5 and 6 were invited to take part in the discussions. Each session included 4 to 5 participants and at least one representative from each of the three WPs. Key questions of the discussions were organised into four themes and communicated to FGD participants in advance. Discussions focused mainly on the prioritisation criteria used for the first cycle, highlighting the most essential criteria within the different WPs and reflecting on those to be used for the next prioritisation round. Policy needs were the second item of discussion, trying to understand what policy needs each WP is trying to address, and their plans for identifying needs for the second round. Next, each WP shared their experience of prioritisation and the difficulties encountered. Finally, light was shed on the lessons learned highlighting what should be done differently. Results of these fruitful discussions were taken into consideration for this second prioritisation round and will be soon documented in an article. The main essential aspects to improve the prioritisation process, mentioned by the participants were:

- Having a transparent prioritisation process even if each WP might require different prioritisation criteria,
- Balancing between meeting short-term regulatory needs and anticipating long-term needs in chemical risk assessment,
- Maintaining alignment and synergy between the WPs and with other EU projects to avoid duplication and ensure continuity of work,
- Ensuring that PARC can make the most of its partnerships in terms of linking projects/activities with potential partners.

As a first step, in order to identify regulatory needs that should be addressed under PARC during years 4 to 7, a questionnaire was sent to the Governing Board members on June 13, 2023. This survey was reviewed by the WPLs, TLs, Task 2.1 partners as well as GB co-chairs. The object was to get a feedback on the choice of questions to ensure a good survey outcome. The questionnaire consisted of five sections, questions were addressed per WP and, the mapping of needs exercise mainly involved WPs 4-5 & 6 dealing with research and innovation activities. WP 7 ensures that data and associated information are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) and, WP9 aims to facilitate the establishment and maintenance of the capacities needed to address current, emerging, and novel challenges in chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment. Thus, WP 7 and WP 9 are more reliant on the priorities of other WPs. WP 8 supports the

¹ Background documents will be elaborated for the prioritised substances in PARC. They should summarise the main research needs, the regulatory status, the on-going or foreseen work planned at EU and/or national levels and synergies that might be developed.

development and consolidation of new concepts and tools that address key challenges of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability; therefore, is closely linked to EC priorities.

At the start of each section of the questionnaire, a short summary of the WP and its different activities was provided. A briefing of the currently addressed substances/groups of substances or endpoints were also provided for each Task. Respondents received the questionnaire in two formats: 1) A Word document with the survey’s questions and instructions, intended to facilitate discussions between colleagues before submitting a final answer, by the Governing Board Principal Representatives (GB PR)², through the 2) Microsoft forms. Respondents were asked to suggest new substances or group of substances, endpoints and even methods and case studies to be included in PARC’s list of priorities for future years. For every nomination, they had to precise the corresponding specific policy or regulatory need. ‘Regulatory’ questions are the short-term immediate need identified by regulatory bodies while ‘Policy’ questions are the bigger picture. PARC is mainly driven by answering regulatory needs, but also considers answering longer-term policy needs. The deadline to complete the survey was set to August 25, 2023. The survey is presented in the Annex. The following figure summarises the various steps of the Mapping of Needs carried out for the second PARC prioritisation round.

Figure 1: Mapping of needs steps under the second prioritisation round of PARC

Alongside this, the three European agencies in PARC: ECHA, EFSA and EEA organised a meeting on June 14, 2023, during which they introduced their Key Areas of Regulatory Challenge (KARC). In fact, ECHA has elaborated a document³ detailing the four KARC they have identified:

- Provide protection against most harmful chemicals
- Addressing chemical pollution in the environment
- Shift away from Animal Testing
- Improved availability on chemical data

This document may be updated as necessary.

The EEA might also establish a document listing the activities of potential interest to them.

These needs will be further discussed and integrated into this prioritisation process.

² PARC’s Governance Structure : <https://www.eu-parc.eu/about-us/governance>

³ Link to KARC document elaborated by ECHA (version of November 2023): [All news - ECHA \(europa.eu\)](https://www.echa.europa.eu/all-news)

3. Survey Results

The response rate was of 87% (26 out of 36 countries). Feedback was received from the European Commission (EU) and, the following countries: Norway, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Spain, Finland, Germany, Sweden, Switzerland, Greece, Iceland, United Kingdom, Hungary, Luxembourg, Italy, France, Portugal, Estonia, Slovenia, Slovakia, Croatia, Denmark, Ireland, Czech Republic, and Austria. The Netherlands contributed through discussions at the GB meeting. Latvia did not submit the mapping of needs survey in time, but expressed the most essential needs that had already been identified and named through an e-mail sent to the PARC CT.

Results were compiled in a Word Document. A three-column table (Suggestion, Policy/Regulatory needs, Nominations) was drawn for each Task. The grouping of substances and groups of substances was quite challenging as some were specific and others broader. This difficulty had already been identified during the first prioritisation cycle and highlighted by several WPLs/TLs. The following tables summarise the survey respondents' nominations (without the policy/regulatory need). EC suggestions have a *light grey* background. The needs are listed in descending order of the times they have been named. Please note that this is a preliminary compilation, and the grouping of substances needs to be discussed for better shaping.

3.1. WP4: Monitoring and exposure

3.1.1. Task 4.1: Human biomonitoring

Substances / groups of substances currently addressed under **Task 4.1** on Human biomonitoring for the **general population** are: *Biocides, pharmaceuticals/hazardous medicinal products, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, metals, mercury, arsenic, phthalates, emerging chemicals, mixtures*. In table 1 the **suggestions** of substances/ groups of substances to be potentially added in the work programme of this task for future years are compiled.

Table 1: Potential Substances / Group of substances to be included in Task 4.1: Human biomonitoring, for the general population

Substance / Group	Nomination
Microplastic and nanoplastic	Norway, Israel, EC, Luxembourg, France, Croatia, Ireland, Czech Republic, Austria, Latvia ⇒ Total: 10
Nanomaterials: Micro (& nano) particles	Belgium, Cyprus, UK, France, Portugal, Croatia, Latvia ⇒ Total: 7
Natural toxins, including: -Mycotoxins like enniatins and alternaria as studied in Wp5 (to complement) -Marine biotoxins -Freshwater biotoxins	Norway, Belgium, Germany, Italy, Portugal ⇒ Total: 5
Flame retardants (FR): legacy & their substitutes including halogenated & organophosphorous & aromatic and aliphatic & others	Belgium, EC, Denmark, Czech Republic ⇒ Total: 4
Lead	Cyprus, Finland, EC, Latvia ⇒ Total: 4
Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)	Luxembourg, Slovenia, Latvia

	⇒ Total: 3
Benzophenones and other UV-filters	EC, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Mineral oil saturated hydrocarbons (MOSH) and Mineral Oil Aromatic Hydrocarbons (MOAH)	EC, Slovenia ⇒ Total: 2
A shift of focus from already regulated chemicals (e.g., flame retardants and phthalates) to the substances used as substitutes for these	Sweden, Denmark ⇒ Total: 2
Air pollutants with EDC properties	Hungary, Latvia ⇒ Total: 2
Chemicals in indoor air	Czech Republic, Latvia ⇒ Total: 2
Vitamins (A, D) from diet/various sources (e.g. supplementation) and products	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Chemicals in active use e.g., Liquid Chrystal Monomers (LCMs)	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Specific chemicals of concern that are regulated under REACH, in particular nonylphenol and DEHTP	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
Persistent chloro-organic substances, such as chlorinated paraffins (short, medium, long chain) and dioxins (PCDD/F – TEQ + dl-PCB TEQ)	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
Environmentally Persistent Pharmaceutical Polluants (EPPPs)	Israel ⇒ Total: 1
Nicotine derivatives, substances and salts	Cyprus ⇒ Total: 1
Persistent Organic Pollutants in human milk	Slovenia ⇒ Total: 1
Nutritional biomarkers	Slovenia ⇒ Total: 1
Heavy metals, including lead, mercury, cadmium, nickel, chromium	Slovakia ⇒ Total: 1
Alternatives/Substitutes to PFAS substances	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Pharmaceuticals	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1
Pesticides	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1
Substances that act on the thyroid axis – (Possibly under REACH/ restriction - group Thyroid Active)	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Para-phenylenediamines (PPDs e.g. 6PPD and its metabolite 6PPD-Quinone)	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Alkylphenols - 4-tert-butylphenol (EC 202-679-0, CAS 98-54-4), 4-heptylphenol (EC 276-743-1 CAS 72624-02-3) and p-dodecylphenol (EC 310-154-3, CAS 121158-58-5)	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Chemical leaching from plastics and rubber tyres	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Organotin compounds	UK ⇒ Total: 1

Substances / groups of substances currently addressed under **Task 4.1** on Human biomonitoring in **occupational settings** are:

- Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys: *Cadmium, PAHs, bisphenols*
- Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system: *PFAS, pesticides, bisphenols, metals, mercury*
- Waste management: *E-waste and plastics, including PVC (household and industrial)*
- Occupational survey in healthcare sector: *Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs); Inhalation anaesthetics; Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)*

For coming years, some suggestions were pointed out by the Working Party on Chemicals (WPC)⁴ and include: Battery chemicals (including lithium, cobalt and nickel salts), substances in welding fumes, bisphenols (including BPA), pesticides/fungicides, nanoparticles and other advanced materials, phthalates and, PFAS. Table 2 lists the survey **suggestions** for substances and substance groups in the occupational field, to be potentially addressed in PARC years 4 to 7.

Table 2: Potential Substances / Group of substances to be included in Task 4.1: Human biomonitoring, for workers

Substance / Group	Nomination
Nanomaterials/particles	Belgium, Sweden, EC, Portugal, Croatia, Latvia ⇒ Total: 6
Substances in welding fumes	Sweden, EC, Croatia, Austria, France, Latvia ⇒ Total: 6
Battery chemicals (including lithium, cobalt, cadmium and nickel salts but also fluorinated compounds and ionic liquids)	Sweden, EC, France, Portugal, Austria ⇒ Total: 5
PFAS, PFAS-related chemical	EC, Ireland, Austria, France ⇒ Total: 4
Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)	Israel, Luxembourg, Croatia ⇒ Total: 3
Bisphenols, including BPA	EC, Austria, France ⇒ Total: 3
Phthalates	EC, Austria, France ⇒ Total: 3
Recycling / disinfection side-/by-products	Portugal, UK, Belgium ⇒ Total: 3
Chromium VI compounds	Spain, Switzerland ⇒ Total: 2
Chemicals associated with plastics	Norway, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Pesticides/fungicide	EC, France ⇒ Total: 2
Mycotoxins in an occupational setting (agricultural, food production)	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Skin sensitisers in consumer/professional mixtures including acrylates and methacrylates & including also substances used in detergents & biocides as used by cleaning staff at individuals' homes	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Lead	Cyprus ⇒ Total: 1
Flame retardants	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Adding some mixture effect-biomarkers and assessment values for Neurotoxicity, Genotoxicity + Oxidative stress	Switzerland ⇒ Total: 1

⁴ The Working Party on Chemicals is an EC-level group, made up of experts from Member States and representatives of employer and worker organisations.

and Reproduction toxicity with WP 4.1.3 on effect-biomarkers	
Consider possible co-exposures to chemicals. These may regard i.e., metals, like Chromium with co-exposure from nickel, and manganese, but also chemical families – such as phthalates, bisphenols, dioxins, poly chlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) or volatile organic compounds (VOC)	Italy ⇒ Total: 1
Alternatives/Substitutes to PFAS	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Alternative/Substitutes to bisphenols	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Neonicotinoid Insecticides	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1
Biocides such as isothiazoles and isothiazolinones	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
PAHs	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Cadmium	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Dinitrogen oxide (for inhalation anaesthetics)	France ⇒ Total: 1
E-waste that is not yet considered e.g. cell phones and solar panels	UK ⇒ Total: 1

3.1.2. Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Task 4.2, aiming to establish an EU-wide environmental and multisource monitoring, is currently addressing the following substances / group of substances: *Biocides, pharmaceuticals/hazardous medicinal products, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, phthalates, endocrine Disrupting Compounds, emerging chemicals, mixtures, PBT/vPBT*. New **suggestions** have been generated from the survey and are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Potential Substances / Group of substances to be included in Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring, and the corresponding matrix

Substance / Group	Matrix	Nomination
Micro- and nano plastics	All environmental media: water (surface and drinking water and sediment), air, soil, biota, food, both temporal and spatial trends, in combination with additional efforts in HBM	Norway, Belgium, Israel, Spain, EC, Luxembourg, France, Croatia, Czech Republic, Austria ⇒ Total: 10
PMT/vPvM (PMTs such as 1,4-dioxane, melamine)	Soil, water (surface water, river bank filtration, groundwater, raw water, drinking water), biota	Switzerland, EC, UK, Luxembourg, Denmark, Germany ⇒ Total: 6
Para-substituted phenylendiamines and similar substances (PPDs e.g. 6PPD and its metabolite 6PPD-Quinone)	Screening of occurrence in water environment in potentially contaminated sites (EU wide).	Finland, Denmark, Austria ⇒ Total: 3
Chemicals leaching from plastics and rubber tyres	- Soils (in agriculture areas) for spatial coverage - Water (drinking water) for spatial coverage - Human matrices such as blood or urine	Norway, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2

	- Air to study exposure and trends	
Particulate matter (Ultrafine particles (UFP) (ambient air) and characterization of its biological/toxic active components, PM2.5)	- UFP monitoring as spectrum 5/10-300 nm in ambient air at urban and “supersites” with time-trend. - Soils (in agriculture areas) for spatial coverage - Water (drinking water) for spatial coverage - Human matrices such as blood or urine	Luxembourg, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Pyrethroids	Pyrethroids are analytically very challenging. Hence, a specialised or “easier to apply” workflow or monitoring design should be developed for them, with regard to both temporal trends and spatial coverage	Germany, Croatia ⇒ Total: 2
Flame retardants: legacy, substitutes (FR), Brominated flame retardants (BFRs) and in particular Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs)	All environmental media: water, air, soil, biota, food, both temporal and spatial trends, in combination with additional efforts in HBM	Belgium, EC ⇒ Total: 2
Lead, inorganic arsenic, cadmium, mercury, nickel and iodine	In specific seaweed species	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Cr(III)	-	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Pollutants in wastewater effluents	Effects of chemicals in surface water	EC ⇒ Total: 1
PFAS	-	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Mineral oil aromatic hydrocarbons (MOAH)	In food	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Nanomaterials	- Soils (in agriculture areas) for spatial coverage - Water (drinking water) for spatial coverage - Human matrices such as blood or urine	Portugal ⇒ Total: 1
Non-intentionally added substances (NIAS), associated to bisphenols, e.g. cyclo-di-BADGE	food & other environmental media as appropriate	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Environmentally Persistent Pharmaceutical Pollutants (EPPPs)	Surface and drinking water. Spatial coverage to allow for the identification of sources and sinks of this family of compounds	Israel ⇒ Total: 1
Within the group biocides, anticoagulant substances used in rodenticides are substances of high concern due to their PBT properties and widely used, especially second-generation anticoagulant (SGARs) such as brodifacoum, bromadiolone, difenacoum, difethialone and flocoumafen	Identify residues of rodenticides in water, sediment and soil and in non-target animals	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
Rodenticides and Veterinary medicines	-	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Pharmaceuticals	General monitoring data in environmental media	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
2-Mercaptobenzothiazole (2-MBT)	Screening of occurrence in water environment in potentially contaminated sites (EU wide)	Finland ⇒ Total: 1

A shift of focus from already regulated chemicals (e.g., flame retardants and phthalates) to the substances used as substitutes for these	Which media that should be prioritised depends on the aims of the studies and which substance groups that are targeted. For screening of new emerging pollutants, it is important to include samples and environments closer to potential sources such as wastewater treatment plants, indoor environment, urban environment, and products. Background sites, far away from known point sources, is important for identifying possible long-range transport. Human exposure through food is also an important aspect	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Chemicals in active use e.g., Liquid Chrystal Monomers (LCMs), are of interest		Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Alkylphenols - 4-tert-butylphenol (EC 202-679-0, CAS 98-54-4), 4-heptylphenol (EC 276-743-1 CAS 72624-02-3) and p-dodecylphenol (EC 310-154-3, CAS 121158-58-5) could be used as exemplar substances		UK ⇒ Total: 1
Alternatives/Substitutes to PFAS	All environmental compartments	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Indoor Dust in addition to VOC	Indoor dust and air, release from (consumer) articles and products	Luxembourg ⇒ Total: 1
Sweeteners and food additives	Emission loads, spatial coverage	Italy ⇒ Total: 1
Herbicides and insecticides	-	France ⇒ Total: 1
Advanced materials		France ⇒ Total: 1
Bis(4-chlorophenyl) sulfone (BCPS, CAS No. 80-07-9)	The most relevant media would be sediment and biota	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Stable Isotopes	-	UK ⇒ Total: 1
PAHs	-	UK ⇒ Total: 1

3.1.3. Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Furthermore, Table 4 lists new suggestions to be potentially included under **Task 4.3** aiming for the development of innovative methods and tools for environmental, food and human monitoring.

Table 4: Suggestions of innovative (self)-sampling and measurement approaches to be included in Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Innovative (self)-sampling and measurement approaches	Nomination
Microplastics: -In complex Matrices -In food and water -Biomonitoring -Harmonisation exercises for the detection of micro/nano plastics and particles in environmental and human biomonitoring	EC, Croatia, Israel, Finland, Austria ⇒ Total: 5
Continue & pursue other work on NTS / SS / EDA / DART MS - Continue work on NTS based on high-resolution mass spectrometry, but also other more accessible/easy techniques such as DART-MS. There is a need for a consultable	Belgium, Czech Republic ⇒ Total: 2

database to allow peak identification. Work on “calibration” and building this database (probable links to WP 8.2 activities)	
Particular effort should be put in place regarding non-invasive human biomatrices such as hair for organic compounds, not only metals	Greece, Italy ⇒ Total: 2
Innovative methods: developing wrist band sampling into a quantitative way to assess skin exposure.	Norway
Further advance HBM & other monitoring methods for nanoparticles	Belgium
Continue current work on EDs: easy to measure health impact markers for EDs, preferably unambiguous & early signals so intervention is still possible	Belgium
(Self)-Sampling of micronutrients in human biosamples e.g. urine.	Israel
Plant protection products in groundwater	Spain
Identification of new effect biomarkers through metabolomic approaches	Finland
Untargeted screening applied to HBM	Germany
PFAS sum-parameter analyses	Germany
Investigate if the exposome approach and new analytical technology within this area may be used in PARC to study the human chemical exposure as well as the human impact.	Sweden
Chromium: Methods capable of distinguishing exposure to Cr(VI)-substances from exposure to other Cr-substances (Cr(III), Cr(0))	EC
Methods and tools for detecting early warning signals of emerging chemical risks in collaboration with WP 8	EC
Monitoring of vulnerable/sensitive human populations, especially in pregnancy and infancy needs to be extended.	UK
Environmental quality sensors	UK
Understanding impact of chemicals on soils biodiversity	UK
Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in human exhaled air by electronic nose (e-Nose)	Portugal
Saliva sampling for genotoxicity assessment (comet assay)	Portugal
Development of analytical methods to assess exposure to nanomaterials in biological samples	Portugal
Apply non-targeted and suspect screening to HBM and make use of the results in EWS	Slovenia
Connect SS/NTS approaches with alternative non-invasive matrices, such as hair, saliva, deciduous teeth, sweat, etc.	Slovenia
Better connect environment-food-human continuum	Slovenia
Suggested monitoring approaches	Ireland
Sensors and new monitoring approaches	Ireland
Biological Effects	Ireland
In the absence of human biomonitoring, monitoring data on chemical occurrences should be used to inform us better about the exposure levels of chemical mixtures and potential threats to ecosystem services or biodiversity	Ireland
Harmonisation exercises for Non-Target Analyses in environmental and human biomonitoring	Austria
Methods for the detection of substances such as PFAS, pesticides and potential POP/PBT substances in air/deposition	Austria

For the methods developed under **Task 4.3**, performance criteria were **suggested** and are summarised in Table 5.

Table 5: Method performance criteria suggested to be privileged as main driver for innovative method development under Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Method performance criteria	Explanation	Nomination
Nutritional uptake - Broad chemical coverage	Nutritional uptake - Broad chemical coverage - since multiple micronutrients exist a broad coverage is needed.	Israel

Broad chemical coverage (fast screening)	Considering the expected large number of samples, fast screening methods will be useful to make timely decisions on whether or not it is worth pursuing further analysis on the samples (more specific, time and cost consuming), by providing a “yes/no” response.	Portugal
Microplastics - Sensitivity	Microplastics - Sensitivity - given variable size distributions and related health effect - a method that is able to distinguish sizes may be needed.	Israel
Sensitivity	Possible health effects resulting from chronic low-level exposures demand lower detection limits in quantitative methods; furthermore, limits of quantification (rather than LoD) should be calculated and further validated by laboratories to increase data quality (decrease uncertainty) for risk assessment.	Portugal
It is recommended to include the aim of using the method in the choice of criteria	The performance criteria depend on the method. E.g. for Screening approaches, the broad chemical coverage is really important as this is one key advantage of the methods and chemicals that are not covered cannot be identified or quantified.	Germany
Specificity	The methods ability to quantify the analyte of interest, even in the presence of interferent is essential to ensure good quality data and reliable risk assessment.	Portugal
Presence absence information is very important for groups of emerging contaminants as well as persistent and mobile chemicals (useful also for trend monitoring).	-	Ireland
Fully validated quantitative methods are needed to ascertain concentrations of chemicals of known concern	-	Ireland
Transformation products and metabolites of persistent and mobile chemicals as well as pharmaceuticals should be included.	-	Ireland
Monitoring required for DNA/RNA in soils alongside mapping genomes for invertebrates in particular prioritising species used within chemicals risk assessment	Use of DNA monitoring would be relevant in identifying species sensitives to chemicals exposure and could be useful for pesticides risk assessment and CLP.	UK

Regarding the harmonisation issue associated to the innovative methods developed within **Task 4.3**, survey respondents were asked to choose between 2 options. The results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Results of the voting on the two options regarding the harmonisation of the innovative methods

Guidelines for common method performance assessment and result reporting but preservation of complementarity of methods	Normalisation through Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) applicable to particular substance classes/matrices	No preference
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Norway, Israel, Spain, Finland, Germany, Sweden, Switzerland, Greece, Iceland, Italy, Estonia, Slovakia, Croatia, Denmark ⇒ Total: 14	Belgium, Cyprus, Hungary, Luxembourg, Portugal, Ireland, Austria ⇒ Total: 7	EC, France, Slovenia, Czech Republic, UK ⇒ Total: 5
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3.2. WP5: Hazard assessment

3.2.1. Task 5.1: Closing data gaps of concern

Besides the substances currently addressed under **Task 5.1** (*BPA alternatives, Natural toxins*), aiming to close data gaps of concern through toxicity testing, survey respondents identified new substances / group of substances to be potentially included in Task 5.1's work programme for the years 4 to 7. These suggestions are listed in Table 7.

Table 7: Suggestions of Substances / Group of substances to be included in Task 5.1: Closing data gaps of concern

Substance / group	Nomination
Micro & nano plastics – data gap for environmental and human health	Norway, Belgium, Israel, Spain, Finland, UK, Croatia, Czech Republic, Austria ⇒ Total: 9
Polymers- Biodegradable polymers (environment)	Switzerland, EC, UK, Portugal ⇒ Total: 4
Work on toxins to be extended, Mycotoxins like Deacetoxyscripenol (DAS), citrinin and patulin	Germany, Italy, Portugal, Norway Total: 4
PFAS	Finland, Switzerland, France ⇒ Total: 3
Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs)	Norway, Israel ⇒ Total: 2
Metals: effects on endocrine system	Greece, Italy ⇒ Total: 2
Residues of medicinal substances: Studies on the human health and environmental effects	France, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Chemicals leaching from plastics	Norway, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Advanced materials (including nanomaterials) (both human health and environment).	Finland, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Food improvement agents - data gap for Human health	Israel, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
2D materials including graphene family	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs)	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Mineral oil hydrocarbons	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Pesticides	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Non-intentionally added substances (NIAS)	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Phthalate alternatives: e.g. for DEHP (e.g. DINCH, TOTM, DEHT and BTHC) to be used in e.g. medical devices (e.g. blood bags,	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1

medical tubes, etc), especially for ED (human & environmental), respiratory sensitising, PMT/vPvM properties	
Co-formulants used in PPP/biocides should be assessed for terrestrial toxicity, as they are highly emitted to the environment	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
Endocrine disruption properties for anticoagulant rodenticides both in mammals for population relevance and in non-target organisms other than mammals (environment)	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
Chlorinated paraffins (short, medium, long chain)	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
BPA: carcinogenic effects, including genotoxic carcinogenesis	Hungary ⇒ Total: 1
Studies on the health effects of SDHIs (Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors) fungicides	France ⇒ Total: 1
Specific mixtures (nanoparticles with Potential Toxic elements (PTEs)) - human health	Portugal ⇒ Total: 1
Alternatives/Substitutes to PFAS substances	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Persistent and pseudo-persistent substances	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Precursor (substances degrading to substances of concern)	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Pharmaceuticals, including antibiotics, and their metabolites	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1
Mixtures	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Triclosan	Austria ⇒ Total: 1

3.2.2. Task 5.2: Innovative tools and methods for toxicity testing

Endpoints currently addressed under **Task 5.2** are: *endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity and, immuno-toxicity.*

Task 5.2 aims to establish innovative tools and methods for toxicity testing. New endpoints have been proposed for coming years under this task and are listed in Table 8.

Table 8: Suggestions of Endpoints to be included in Task 5.2: Innovative tools and methods for toxicity testing

Endpoint	Nomination
Developmental and reproductive toxicity (DART)	Norway, Germany, UK, France ⇒ Total: 4
Cardiovascular system including epithelial function	Norway, Finland ⇒ Total: 2
Respiratory system	Norway, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Characterisation of MOCS (More than One Constituent Substance)	EC, Czech Republic ⇒ Total: 2
A systemic approach to addressing (persistent) fibre toxicity with consideration on parameters contributing to different adverse outcomes, and possibility to use them in regulatory context (i.e. beyond WHO fibre paradigm)	EC ⇒ Total: 1

Further general development of New Assessment Methods (NAMs) that can replace animal testing for hazard endpoints where this is not possible today	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Intestinal microbiome	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
PMT & vPvM – chronic aquatic & soil toxicity	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
PBT & vPvB – chronic aquatic & soil toxicity	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Transgenerational effects	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Glucose tolerance / Insulin sensitivity - Streptozotocin (STZ) as a positive control substance	Israel ⇒ Total: 1
Inflammation - Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) as a positive control substance	Israel ⇒ Total: 1
Terrestrial toxicity	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
New methods to evaluate the potential of PFAS polymers and precursors to form stable terminal PFASs	Finland ⇒ Total: 1
Behaviour endpoints are urgently needed for environmental risk assessment	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
Shift from standard toxicity endpoints to look at modes of action of toxicants, i.e., MIEs such as receptor binding	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Environmental endpoints / responses (ecotoxicity generally underrepresented)	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Evaluation of transformation products / metabolites, which can be more toxic than the parent compounds	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Genotoxicity and non-genotoxic carcinogenicity	Portugal ⇒ Total: 1
Genotoxic carcinogenicity	Hungary ⇒ Total: 1
General organ toxicity after repeated exposure	Italy ⇒ Total: 1
Toxicokinetics	Italy ⇒ Total: 1
Methods to assess the effects of chemicals on biodiversity	France ⇒ Total: 1
Harmonised omics-based methods	Portugal ⇒ Total: 1
Immunotoxicity	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Neurotoxicity	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Thyroidea endpoint relevant for endocrine disruption	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
Development of in vitro assays for comparative liver enzyme induction in different species.	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Micro and nano-sized materials including fibres	Austria ⇒ Total: 1

Endocrine Disrupters (ED)	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
To address the knowledge gaps in understanding bioaccumulation and biological effects of CECs, a rapid contaminant screening assay adapting a biophysical assay to classify drug molecule mammalian plasma membrane permeability, matching organism lipid/sterol composition to published data, could be used. This type of screening method could be used to assess the risk of any new chemicals by their ability to cross a biological membrane.	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1
Environmental risk assessment can routinely utilize invertebrate reproduction/intergenerational effects as an indicator of low concentration chemical impacts. Studies of low concentration effects are lacking and can provide information of chronic intergenerational effects. Selection of a suitable organism that can be used in a harmonized protocol is the challenge.	Ireland ⇒ Total: 1

New data generated in tasks 5.1 and 5.2 as well as relevant data from databases will be mapped to existing (networks of) Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), with the aim to hypothesise adverse outcomes. This will feed into **Task 5.3** which deals with quantitative systems toxicology and AOP development.

3.3. WP6: Innovation in Regulatory Risk Assessment

3.3.1. Task 6.1: Integrated approaches to testing and assessment of chemicals

The aim of **Task 6.1** is to establish IATAs (Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment) to be used for different European regulations on chemical safety for different industry sectors as well as for the CLP Regulation (Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulation, (EC) No 1272/2008). Health effects currently covered under this Task include: *Endocrine disruption (thyroid hormone synthesis disruption; anti-androgenic effects), genotoxicity and systemic target organ toxicity (initial focus on liver fibrosis)*. New **suggestions** of health effects to be potentially included in the work programme of years 4 to 7 were identified in the survey and are documented in Table 9.

Table 9: Suggestions of Endpoints to develop IATAs for under Task 6.1: Integrated approaches to testing and assessment of chemicals

Endpoint for IATA	Nomination
Neurotoxicity	Belgium, Israel, Spain, UK, Portugal, Czech Republic, Austria ⇒ Total: 7
Immunotoxicity	Belgium, Spain, Germany, UK, Portugal, Czech Republic, Austria ⇒ Total: 7
ED for environment	Spain, Denmark, Czech Republic ⇒ Total: 3
Non-genotoxic carcinogenesis	Norway, Germany ⇒ Total: 2
Metabolic – Glucose tolerance / Insulin sensitivity	Israel, Germany ⇒ Total: 2
IATAs for environmental assessments	Germany, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Thyroidea endpoint relevant for endocrine disruption	Denmark, Austria Total: 2

How to use NAMs for hazards assessment	Sweden, Denmark ⇒ Total: 2
Non-EATS EDC (not oestrogen, androgen, thyroid, or steroidogenesis-related endocrine-disrupting chemicals)	Norway, Austria ⇒ Total: 2
Genotoxicity of nanomaterials	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Developmental Neurotoxicity	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Transgenerational effects, epigenetics and delayed effects	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Inflammatory	Israel ⇒ Total: 1
Sensitisation	Finland ⇒ Total: 1
Ecotoxicity – or applicability of the above endpoints (neurotoxicity and immunotoxicity) for ecotox species also (e.g., fish, daphnids, earthworms etc.)	UK ⇒ Total: 1

3.3.2. Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Under **Task 6.2** aiming to propose an integrated approach for risk assessment (multiple sources, life environments, mixtures, exposure through life with PBK, risk assessment and health impact), groups of substances currently undergoing risk assessment are:

- Aggregate exposure: *PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures, Bisphenols and Phthalates*.
- PBPk: *PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures, Bisphenols and Mycotoxins*.
- Real-life mixtures: *PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures and Mycotoxins*.
- Health Impact Assessment: *PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures and Bisphenols*.

Table 10 shows additional substances/groups of substances identified in the survey as high priorities for risk assessment.

Table 10: Suggestions of Substances / Groups of substances to be included under Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment:

Substance / Group	Nomination
ED mixtures: - ED mixtures in the environment & for human health - Aggregate exposure to different endocrine disruptors from different source	Belgium, EC, Czech Republic, Austria ⇒ Total: 4
Biocides	Israel, Finland, UK ⇒ Total: 3
Health impact assessment of flame retardants	Belgium, Spain ⇒ Total: 2
Air pollution components including ultrafine particles	Norway, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Further development of methods for health and environmental risk assessment of co-exposures to multiple chemicals	EC, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Aggregate exposure from 'Mixtures' in view of 'MOCS'	EC ⇒ Total: 1
Mixtures – what is trapped on drinking water filters (e.g. Britta) i.e. what is in drinking water	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Real-life mixtures cleaning staff at individuals' homes & real-life mixtures maintenance & cleaning workers at industrial sites are being exposed to (link with 4.1)	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Combination effects (multiple exposure from different source/mixtures)	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1

Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC)	Luxembourg ⇒ Total: 1
Mycotoxins	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Welding fumes	Finland ⇒ Total: 1
AOP-networks / Aggregate Exposure Pathways (AEPs) – internal /external exposures	UK ⇒ Total: 1
The additional ones implemented in WP4 and WP5, establishing a collaborative link	Italy ⇒ Total: 1
Nanomaterials	Portugal ⇒ Total: 1
Persistent organic pollutants (dioxins, furans, PCBs)	Slovenia ⇒ Total: 1
Alternatives/Substitutes to PFAS substances	Denmark ⇒ Total: 1
PPDs+ quinones: para-phenylenediamines (PPDs e.g. 6PPD and its metabolite 6PPD-Quinone)	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
Products containing perfume	Austria ⇒ Total: 1

3.3.3. Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Task 6.3 is responsible for reviewing the effectiveness of risk assessment methodologies and reviews are based on case studies addressing specific substances and effects as well as the general use of tools, criteria, and methods.

-Currently addressed effects are: *Endocrine Disruption, Skin sensitization, Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity, and Developmental neurotoxicity*

-Currently addressed substances/ groups of substances are: *Biocides, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, phthalates, endocrine disrupting compounds, mixtures, food contact material, cosmetics, PBT/vPvB.*

-Currently addressed tools, criteria, and methods are: *risk-based decision benchmarks, methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk, quantitative expressions of uncertainty, chemical data gap filling approaches, protection of ecosystems, secondary poisoning, occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants, and workplace chemical risk assessment.*

Table 11 shows additional **suggestions** for aspects related to the effectiveness of risk assessment methodologies, including potential inconsistencies and/or harmonisation needs, to be potentially reviewed for years 4 to 7 of PARC.

Table 11: Suggestions of Case studies to be included under Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Suggestion	Country
Structure based risk assessment of chemicals as a chemical data gap filling approaches	Israel, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Nanomaterials. This type of materials are present in almost every sector and uncertainties exist for their risk assessment. Therefore, new methodologies for the risk assessment of nanomaterials are needed	Spain, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Occupational health in recycling facilities	UK, Portugal ⇒ Total: 2
Consideration of confidence levels when assessing uncertainty in exposure, emission and risk assessment: when exposure, emission or risk estimates need to be compared with legally defined maximum acceptable or tolerable emission, exposure or risk limit values, then it is important to know the uncertainty and	EC ⇒ Total: 1

associated confidence level of the calculated or modelled or otherwise estimated exposure, emission or risk values. The question is: which quantitative confidence level (50%? 67%, 90%? 95%? 99%?) can be proposed as useful in decision-making; and does the required confidence level depend on the kind of risk being assessed?	
Adequate considerations of chemicals where morphology of material may dictate relevant aspects of risk assessment (e.g. fibres, particles, nanomaterials)	EC ⇒ Total: 1
CLP classification using NAMs	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
The use of NAMs in the setting of OELS: implementation needs	Norway ⇒ Total: 1
Case studies on other neurotoxicity endpoints: human health & environment (e.g. social behaviour)	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Specific risk assessment methodology for vulnerable populations, e.g. babies, children & teenagers	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Expanding work on mixture exposure assessment: including occupational health & also NIAS	Belgium ⇒ Total: 1
Evaluating the environmental risk assessment for substances of natural origin used in PPP and biocides	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
FOCUS models. They are used for the assessment of potential groundwater/surface water contamination. However, inputs used for the modelling should be reviewed, because due to the climate change some agro-climatic parameters might have changed and thus the results could not be real	Spain ⇒ Total: 1
Methods regarding the assessment of metals and metal compounds including metal nanoparticles and alloys	Finland ⇒ Total: 1
Adapt the current risk assessment methodology to address a) highly persistent substances and b) substances with other unacceptable hazardous properties	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
It should be evaluated if every possible use of a chemical product should be granted (e.g. fragrance for washing), if the societal benefit is limited, but a high and unnecessary exposure to these chemicals is resulting	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
Investigate how to better address the effects on/risks to biodiversity loss	Germany ⇒ Total: 1
In general, we would like to see more inclusion of research relating to risk management	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Socioeconomic analysis as a basis for decision making and implementing risk management measures (need to further develop, integrate and bridge the work of risk assessment and risk reduction/management) and to assess the possibilities for substitution	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Risk assessment of non-threshold carcinogens (harmonization needs) in the occupational setting	Sweden ⇒ Total: 1
Monitor the implementation of the requirement to register polymers under REACH (when it happens)	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Compare data required for the implementation of the safe-and-sustainable-by-design criteria framework with data requirements	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Alignment of dietary exposure calculation approaches (incl. food consumption survey data, toxicological reference values and MRLs/indicative levels) across regulatory silos (pesticide/biocides/vetmeds/food contaminants)	UK ⇒ Total: 1
Review of the impact of new CLP hazard classes (PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM, EDC) on the procedure and methodologies to derive environmental limit values (such as EQS)	Luxembourg ⇒ Total: 1
Establish community of experts and stakeholders that would be in constant communication loop that would enable the establishment of a perpetual dialogue between the research needs and aims on one hand and regulatory/policy needs and goals on the other. Namely, it has been shown, that the communication among stakeholders and the public has been one of the strongest means of identifying and addressing the human health related issues	Slovenia ⇒ Total: 1
Disinfection by-products	Austria ⇒ Total: 1

AI based tools to retrieve information, support/facilitate and integrate the use of NAMs (in line with ECHA & EFSA approaches)	Austria ⇒ Total: 1
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3.3.4. Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Lastly, Task 6.4 aims at transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies.

In the first period they have developed activities around four regulatory areas of importance:

- 1) *Developing risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures (across regulatory frameworks)*
- 2) *Facilitating the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (e.g. criteria for the use of NAMs)*
- 3) *Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy (including methods to improve enforcement of chemicals legislation)*
- 4) *Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity (starting initially with plant protection products)*

Other areas identified in the survey where activities should be developed as part of this task are shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Suggestions of Case studies to be included under Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Suggestion	Country
Mixture Assessment Factor - opportunities and pitfalls	Norway
Continue work on in vitro - in vivo extrapolation & uncertainty of NAMs & IATAs	Belgium
Neurotoxicity risk assessment incl. (pre)validated NAMs & IATA: human & environmental health	Belgium
Immunotoxicity risk assessment incl. (pre)validated NAMs & IATA: human & environmental health	Belgium
Increasing harmonization of risk assessment strategies with dedicated programs and tools that promote informed data driven actions and risk management decisions	Israel
There is a need for an updated risk-benefit assessment of fish consumption that takes exposure to methyl mercury, metals, arsenic, PCDD/Fs and DL-PCBs into account.	Germany
Development of a European database in which all approved/registered substances (REACH, biocides, PPPs, pharmaceuticals) are listed and regulatory and industrial information are summarized, most important e.g. tonnage/sales data, the approved applications (i.e. quantities, locations, extent), and monitoring results, together with the respective threshold values	Germany
Provide information to the user of chemical products regarding the potential impact of the considered use	Germany
In general, we would like to see more inclusion of research relating to risk management, and more specifically, in the area of food contaminants	Sweden
Development of information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in waste	Sweden
Risk assessment methods for chemicals in articles with a lifecycle perspective. Development of methods (including fast and efficient analytical methods) to enforce the upcoming PFAS restriction in articles and products	Sweden
Soil risk assessment (indicators)	Switzerland
Methods validation	France
Work task on the development of HBM guidance values, allowing for direct assessment of HBM samples and assist with the effectiveness of communication risk assessment outcomes	Ireland
Further development of a <i>next generation environmental risk assessment</i> , which has already been initiated in collaboration with WP2.2 "NGRAroute, WP4 and WP6, coordination of environmental research in PARC and potential external resources (regulatory relevance: this is also in line with the priorities of ECHA (see also ECHA: key area of regulatory challenges, 2023: e.g.: 2.2.2: "Expanding protection of	Austria

biodiversity by use of NAMs” EFSA (ERA: strategic alignment) and EEA (CSS, indicators, use of NTA, early warning system)	
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4. Discussion

The compilation of survey results was shared with Task 2.1 partners and members of the Management and Governing Boards and discussed at several meetings. There was general agreement that the mapping of needs was a valuable exercise. The Netherlands, however, pointed out that the results would produce long wish lists, and were more in favour of setting up working groups and holding discussions. Furthermore, various points were raised concerning:

1- Refining the results:

It was agreed that clear needs should be defined and their compliance with the framework of PARC should be checked. It was reminded that PARC should not interfere with the work of scientific bodies and that PARC activities should not lead to experimental results only useful for scientific research. Focusing on the regulatory relevance was also brought to discussion. This led to the identification of a gap in the understanding of ‘regulatory relevance’ and the need of further discussion to be clear on this topic.

A good way of refining the results and having clear policy and regulatory needs is to have substance/ endpoint dossiers for needs nominated in the survey. Since the results of the survey are huge to process and, making dossiers for each need is quite a long job, for feasibility reasons, substance / endpoint dossiers will only be produced for the top nominees, i.e. those nominated more than 3 times. It is important to note that GB members have not had the opportunity to support the ideas expressed by other countries, so the number of nominations may have changed. Each substance/ endpoint dossier will include fact sheets for each need. The fact sheet will have different sections:

- Research question,
- Objectives,
- Timeframe to deliver the results,
- Concerned WP,
- Identified by EU agencies (ECHA, EFSA, EEA),
- Initiatives outside PARC addressing this need,
- Resources,
- Feasibility,
- Nomination.

The template should however be further discussed. These fact sheets should deliver key information easy to extract. It's important to note that resources are needed to review the fact sheets and support their development. Task 2.1, in collaboration with the CT, will take the initiative and has already started drafting them. In addition, for some sections (e.g. feasibility and resources), WPLs and TLs need to discuss with their WP/task partners to check what can be done. This will enable a top-down and bottom-up approach as this is a co-funded partnership and the partners’ interests should be considered.

Another challenge is the grouping of substances and endpoints. It was widely agreed that certain groups should be better steered as they are not scientifically relevant.

2- Weighting of the nominations:

It is important to discuss weights of the nominations (between the national and EC levels) and decide if some should have greater weight and therefore more impact than others. This is linked with the alignment of needs between the EC and national level.

3- Checking the needs' feasibility:

The involvement of WPLs and TLs in this step is important in order to identify and eliminate expressed needs that are not technically feasible. Work began at the joint GB/MB session on November 15, 2023, in Madrid, on needs related to micro/nanoplastics and/or particulates, which were most frequently named in the needs mapping survey. Some suggested that it was not easy to meet these needs within the PARC framework. Discussions focused on: i) the scope of the nano or micro plastics/particles/materials cluster, ii) synergies with other initiatives outside PARC - several PARC partners are involved in ongoing nano and micro plastics initiatives - and iii) what is achievable within PARC and what is unachievable due to feasibility issues or resource constraints. The working group encountered some terminology problems due to differing definitions. It was agreed that Chemical Leaders (CL) for nanoplastics and a CL for nanomaterials would be named.

4- Balancing ongoing work with new needs:

A retrospective review of what has been done is clearly necessary to identify easy additions to projects already underway. It is also essential to know what budget is still available for new projects, i.e. to check capacity. The aim is not to jeopardise the work already designed on the priorities agreed in the first round.

5- Aligning the needs expressed by GB members with the national needs:

A strategic discussion should take place at national level to explore ways of providing adequate resources if GB members want PARC to work on particular issues.

6- Making links with the identified KARC:

The KARC identified by the European agencies ([ECHA](#), EFSA, EEA), have proved to be a very important and valuable piece of work. An extraction of the needs identified in these KARC documents has been made by the PARC CT, and WPLs/TLs have been asked to reflect about whether PARC can meet or plans to meet these needs, and if not, why, taking into account their WP/task partners' interests.

7- Avoiding the duplication of work:

Even if some work is being carried out outside PARC on specific subjects that are also being addressed within PARC, there is still a lot of work and research to be done, and PARC's contribution remains valuable. However, to be effective, synergy and good communication are essential. PARC must not duplicate or interfere with the work of science policy or regulatory instruments. [SYNnet](#) is a network designed to facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing with other initiatives focusing on environmental, food, and human health issues and organizations working in the field of chemical risk assessment.

8- Having different consultations throughout the process:

Consultation with National Hubs (NHs), Stakeholder Forum (SF) and the International Board (IB) is planned, but the exact process still needs to be defined. The NH and SF could help rank the needs, and the IB consultation could be a useful way of avoiding duplication of work and keeping abreast of ongoing projects outside PARC. The GB will also be consulted to examine how needs are being translated into concrete projects.

9- Having a transparent process:

A transparent process is crucial. Criteria for selecting priorities (e.g. number of applications, feasibility) should be agreed on during meetings.

10- Having real impact addressing regulatory needs:

Involving regulators through PARCroute could be an idea to ensure that PARC have a real impact in addressing regulatory needs. In fact, PARC plans to develop a series of strategic roadmaps guiding step-by-step to the uptake of innovative science into the regulatory practice of chemical risk assessment in the EU. The first one will be NGRAroute, an activity to implement Next Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA) in all major legislations on chemicals in the EU.

Finally, having substance / endpoint dossiers and fact sheets would simplify the work and allow to have an informed discussion about the different topics. Integrating the needs into factsheet brings them in a format closer to that of projects. It is also a good way of digesting the huge amount of information prior to consultation input. A step-by-step approach will be discussed and approved at forthcoming meetings, identifying what can and cannot be done, taking into account budgetary constraints.

After mapping the needs, it is imperative to refine the results. This should be done between December 2023 and mid-March 2024 by:

- 1) Determining whether PARC can make a contribution to the identified KARCs and,
- 2) Better defining the needs identified in the survey through a substance / endpoint dossiers and fact sheets.

This will help prepare for a workshop to discuss the needs and check their feasibility, specifying what PARC can add to its work programme. Support from WPL, TL and CLs is needed to complete the fact sheets and for the workshop, which could last two days. The workshop will probably take place at ANSES (France) between mid and end of March. Once the needs are better defined and reduced to a shorter list based on feasibility, consultation with NHs and SFs will be essential to rank the needs and ensure alignment with national needs and, the support of the IB will be necessary to check initiatives carried out outside PARC to avoid duplication of work. The steps for this prioritisation process are illustrated in figure 2. Steps 3 and 4 need to be confirmed with MB members, therefore a question mark is added.

Figure 2: Mapping of Needs proposal, global steps

5. Conclusion

The mapping of needs survey, for the second prioritisation round, gave excellent coverage of the needs, but the wish list is too long. This deliverable reports the needs identified in the survey sent to GB members on June 2023. Task 2.1 partners, in collaboration with the CT, have begun drafting fact sheets on these needs in order to better define them. Support from WPLs and TLs is needed, and could be effectively provided through workshops. Consultations with other PARC entities are also planned. All this will lead to the identification of priorities that PARC should include in its work programme for its second half (years 4 to 7). If urgent priorities arise, it will always be possible to integrate them in PARC's work plan through the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) developed in the deliverable D2.5 "Rapid Response Report". As indicated in the report, requests will be assessed in terms of eligibility and feasibility and, for each request, a "response document" will be drawn up to explain the rationale for addressing it or not within the PARC framework.

Annex

“Mapping of needs” survey identifying the priorities for the second half of PARC

Context:

In order to best achieve the objectives of PARC and address regulatory/policy needs at EU and/or National level, **Task 2.1 “Priority setting”**, in charge of coordinating the prioritisation process under PARC, aims to **map the needs** identified by regulators and concerned parties for the second part of PARC, i.e. **years 4 to 7**. The suggested priorities and needs will then be compiled and discussed through meetings and workshops to screen the most relevant ones while giving great attention to their feasibility. Another prioritisation round will take place at the end of the partnership to identify PARC's legacy. In addition, a Rapid Response Mechanism will be put in place to enable emerging needs and emerging priorities to get on board.

This questionnaire has five sections. Questions are addressed per Workpackage (WP) and, the mapping of needs exercise will mainly involve WPs 4-5 & 6. At the start of each section, a short summary of the WP and its different activities will be provided, you are kindly invited to take a good look at these questions and provide your inputs, defining the areas to be addressed in the years 4 to 7 of PARC.

Important is to note that WP 7 ensures that data and associated information are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) and, WP9 aims to facilitate the establishment and maintenance of the capacities needed to address current, emerging, and novel challenges in chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment. Thus, WP 7 and WP 9 are more reliant on the priorities of other WPs. On the other hand, WP 8 supports the development and consolidation of new concepts and tools that address key challenges of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability; therefore, is closely linked to EC priorities.

Another important aspect worth mentioning is that the terms policy and regulatory needs are often used interchangeably. Regulatory questions are the short-term immediate need identified by regulatory bodies while policy questions are the bigger picture. PARC is mainly driven by answering regulatory needs, but also considers answering longer-term policy needs.

For the mapping of needs, an input from the GB, GSB, MB and NH members replying national coordination as well as outreach to national stakeholders is expected, including with members of important related EU projects to encourage synergies.

Attached to the email through which the survey link was sent to you, you can find a *Word* document to facilitate the exchange of the survey questions between colleagues before filling in a final answer on behalf of your institution / country, on the online version.

Please note that,

- this questionnaire is not long but requires a fair amount of time to reflect before filling it out,
- if you need a brief overview of what has already been achieved in the first year of the partnership, this [link](#) will lead you to the annual summary report Y1,
- when you are asked to suggest additional substances / group of substances, you can specify substances within the substance group, if you already have a vision,
- there are no wrong answers, you have to fill it all at once since the answers are not saved.

You are kindly asked to fill in this form *by 04/07/2023*.

I hereby agree to participate in this survey. I acknowledge and agree to the processing of my contact information for the mapping of needs. I will not be asked for any information that identifies me personally. There will be no personal benefit from my participation, other than contributing to science.

(ANSES, represented by its Director General, is responsible for processing personal data in the framework of the preparation and the implementation of the European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals. ANSES collects professional

personal data (name, organisation and organisation address, professional email address and phone number) that are used for the different communication needs during the preparation and the implementation of the Partnership. The ANSES Data Protection Officer is the ANSES Director of the Legal Affairs Department (saisine-daj@anses.fr). The data are kept during the preparation, the implementation and up to 5 years after the end of the Partnership. In accordance with the provisions of REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation - GDPR) and the amended French Data Protection Act of the 6th of January 1978, you have the right to access, rectify, limit and in some cases delete your personal information. You may also, for legitimate reasons, oppose the processing of your personal data. The personal information collected from you in the framework of the Partnership and its implementation is transmitted to the persons involved in the Partnership. You can access your personal information by contacting PARC@anses.fr. If you consider, after having contacted us, that your rights arising from the French Data Protection Act are not respected, you can make a complaint to the CNIL (Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés - the French Commission on Data Protection.)

Feedback form

Contact details:

Name of your institution:

Country:

Email address:

Does your institution have an experience in regulatory and policy needs identification? *(Either participating in evolving the regulatory framework at EU and national level or actively participating in the meetings of competent authority and bringing topics of regulatory need to the discussions)*

- Yes
- No

Is your institution human health risk or environmental risk oriented? (Multiple choice)

- Human health risk assessment
- Human health risk management
- Environmental health risk assessment
- Environmental health risk management
- None of the above

Which of the following best describes your current employment?

- Academia (e.g., university)
- Research institute
- Public health institute
- Industry (e.g., business, company)
- Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and Non-Profit Organisations (NPOs)
- Regulatory authority or agency (e.g., government, EFSA, ECHA)
- Scientific organisations and committees (e.g., WHO, OECD, ILSI-ELSI, SCCS)
- Other. What?

Which of the following best describes your involvement in PARC?

- Governing Board (GB)
- Grant Signatory Board (GSB)
- International Board (IB)
- Management Board (MB)
- National Hub (NH)
- Stakeholder Forum (SF)

Workpackage 4: Monitoring and exposure

Background:

WP4 aims to generate reliable Europe-wide FAIR data on human internal and environmental exposure, a better understanding of the environmental and human exposure to chemicals, their interactions, and uptake from multiple sources including pathways of exposure between the environment and humans. In support of a “one substance, one assessment approach” new monitoring approaches will also be applied to complement existing monitoring schemes. The work under WP4 is divided into three tasks:

- **Task 4.1** carrying the human biomonitoring platform (General HBM survey, Derivation of HBM GV, Roadmap linking HBM Health, Sustain HBM System, Data Analysis within HBM4EU)
- **Task 4.2** establishing an EU-wide environmental and multisource monitoring. Monitoring studies will be performed to provide missing exposure data for an integrated assessment of pollution affecting the environment and our health.
- **Task 4.3** aiming for the development of innovative methods and tools for environmental, food and human monitoring; e.g.: innovative (self-)sampling and chemical profiling approaches addressing either general (waste water base epidemiology) or specific population groups such as mother-child (perinatal exposure) or occupational population. A framework for Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) in which suspect screening and non-targeted screening (NTS) based on high-resolution mass spectrometry are embedded, will be developed.

Task 4.1: Human biomonitoring

Substances / groups of substances currently addressed under Task 4.1 on human biomonitoring for the **general population** are: *Biocides, pharmaceuticals/hazardous medicinal products, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, metals, mercury, arsenic, phthalates, emerging chemicals, mixtures.*

In your opinion, are there other additional substances / substances groups that should be addressed under Task 4.1 for years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/policy need for every suggestion otherwise your request will not be taken into account (If possible specify the regulation reference + which process if possible e.g.: REACH restriction, classification, development of methods for endpoints for the information requirement, BPR, surface and drinking water ...)

Substances / groups of substances currently addressed under Task 4.1 on human biomonitoring in **occupational settings** are:

- Feasibility study to evaluate occupational exposure in general surveys: Cadmium, PAHs, bisphenols
- Assessment of exposure through a sentinel surveillance system: PFAS, pesticides, bisphenols, metals, mercury
- Waste management: E-waste and plastics, including PVC (household and industrial)
- Occupational survey in healthcare sector: Hazardous medicinal products (including cytotoxic drugs); Inhalation anaesthetics; Disinfectant and cleaning products (including biocides)

For coming years, some suggestions were pointed out by the Working Party on Chemicals (WPC) and include: Battery chemicals (including lithium, cobalt and nickel salts), substances in welding fumes, bisphenols (including BPA), pesticides/fungicides, nanoparticles and other advanced materials, phthalates and, PFAS.

Do you identify other substances or substance groups in the occupational field that should be addressed in years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)

- Kindly explain the regulatory/policy need for every suggestion otherwise your request will not be taken into account (If possible specify the regulation reference + which process if possible e.g.: REACH restriction, classification, development of methods for endpoints for the information requirement, BPR, surface and drinking water ...)

Task 4.2: Environmental and multisource monitoring

Substances / groups of substances currently addressed under Task 4.2 on environmental and multisource monitoring are: *Biocides, pharmaceuticals/hazardous medicinal products, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, metals, mercury, arsenic, phthalates, endocrine Disrupting Compounds, emerging chemicals, mixtures, PBT/vPBT*

In your opinion, are there additional substances / substances groups that should be addressed under Task 4.2 on environmental and multisource monitoring for years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Which monitoring data is necessary? This includes information on matrix, kind of monitoring and the objective (e.g. temporal trends, spatial coverage...)

Please specify these information for each suggestion you have just made.
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/ policy need for every suggestion (If possible specify the regulation reference + which process if possible e.g.: REACH restriction, classification, development of methods for endpoints for the information requirement, BPR, surface and drinking water ...)

Task 4.3: Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Kindly suggest innovative (self)-sampling and measurement approaches (in food, environmental or human samples) that should be addressed under Task 4.3. In case this appears relevant to you, please specify particular substance classes and biological matrices to be considered/prioritised.

(This might be a follow-up work on some specific substances included in Task 4.1 or Task 4.2 to map out the exposure / You can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)

- Please explain the regulatory/ policy need and data gap for every suggestion

For the methods developed within Task 4.3 do you have any suggestion of method performance criteria to be privileged as main driver for innovative method development (e.g. sensitivity, qualitative vs semi-quantitative, unambiguous identification of the detected markers, broad chemical coverage...)?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions)
 - Kindly explain your choice for every suggestion

Regarding the harmonization issue associated to the innovative methods developed within Task 4.3, which option would appear more relevant to you among the following:

- Normalisation through Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) applicable to particular substance classes/matrices
- Guidelines for common method performance assessment and result reporting but preservation of complementarity of methods
 - Kindly explain your choice

Under this WP (WP4), do you identify issues you would like to raise that are not covered by the current questions?

Workpackage 5: Hazard assessment

Background:

The overall goal of WP5 is to overcome the major challenges in hazard assessment for human and environmental health. The work under WP5 is divided into three tasks:

- **Task 5.1** aiming to close data gaps of concern through toxicity testing
- **Task 5.2** establishing innovative tools and methods for toxicity testing like comprehensive testing strategies that combine novel methods with well-established approaches addressing specific toxicological endpoints
- **Task 5.3** addressing quantitative systems toxicology and AOP development in order to contribute to the improvement of mechanistic understanding of toxicity and modelling approaches such as PBPK modelling. New data generated in tasks 5.1 and 5.2 as well as relevant data from databases will be mapped to existing (networks of) AOPs, with the aim to hypothesise adverse outcomes.

Task 5.1: Closing data gaps of concern

Beside the substances currently addressed under Task 5.1 (*BPA alternatives, Natural toxins*), do you identify substances with data gaps of concern that should be included in the work for the years 4 to 7 of PARC? (Important is to note that data gaps covered by PARC should not be addressed by industrials under REACH)

- No
- Yes
 - Please suggest a substance/ substance group and its data gap of concern (you can add up to 6 suggestions, considering a total of 3 relevant suggestions for human health and 3 for the environment, start with the high priority one in each category and specify whether the suggested substance and its related data gap is relevant for human health or for the environment).
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/policy need for every suggestion

Task 5.2: Innovative tools and methods for toxicity testing

Endpoints currently addressed under Task 5.2 are: endocrine disruption, metabolic disruption, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity and, immuno-toxicity.

In your opinion, are there other endpoints for human health and environmental risk assessment that should be addressed under Task 5.2 for years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your endpoint suggestion and specify the mode of action (You can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/ policy need for every suggestion

What substance do you suggest to use as test compound for the innovative methods that will be developed under Task 5.2 (years 4 to 7 of PARC)? Please suggest substances for each of the toxicological endpoint and justify your choice.

Under this WP (WP5), do you identify issues you would like to raise that are not covered by the current questions?

Workpackage 6: Innovation in Regulatory Risk Assessment

Background:

The overall goal of WP6 is to drive innovation in regulatory risk assessment by strengthening its scientific basis, with implementation of NGRA as ultimate goal. The work in WP6 is divided into four tasks.

- **Task 6.1** establishing IATAs (Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment) to be used for different European regulations on chemical safety for different industry sectors as well as for the CLP Regulation.
- **Task 6.2** developing innovative and practical approaches for human health risk and impact assessment of single, aggregated and combined exposure to chemicals via multiple sources across regulatory silos and routes during lifetime and, fostering their regulatory uptake.
- **Task 6.3** establishing reviews of risk assessment methodologies' effectiveness within and across relevant chemical sectors through a series of case studies. The case studies will provide science-based support for method development, identify R&I needs as well as suggest improvements and harmonisation opportunities.
- **Task 6.4** transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies. This task will support regulatory processes for reducing risks to humans and the environment by undertaking scenario-based case-studies resulting in guidance documents and/or recommendations.

Task 6.1: Integrated approaches to testing and assessment of chemicals

Under Task 6.1 IATAs for a selected set of health effects are developed and evaluated through dedicated case studies. Health effects currently covered under this Task include: Endocrine disruption (thyroid hormone synthesis disruption; anti-androgenic effects), genotoxicity and systemic target organ toxicity (initial focus on liver fibrosis). Additionally, a harmonized workflow for human relevance assessment is developed.

In addition to the above mentioned IATAs, for what other endpoints should Task 6.1 develop IATAs in years 4 to 7?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/ policy need for every suggestion

Task 6.2: Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Under Task 6.2 aiming to propose an integrated approach for risk assessment (multiple sources, life environments, mixtures, exposure through life with PBK, risk assessment and health impact), groups of substances currently undergoing risk assessment are:

- Aggregate exposure: PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures, Bisphenols and Phthalates.
- PBPK: PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures, Bisphenols and Mycotoxins.
- Real-life mixtures: PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures and Mycotoxins.
- Health Impact Assessment: PFAS, Metals, Pesticides, Mixtures and Bisphenols.

In your opinion, are there additional substances / groups of substances of high priority for risk assessment between years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/policy need for every suggestion

Task 6.3: Review of risk assessment methodology

Task 6.3 is responsible for reviewing the effectiveness of risk assessment methodologies; the reviews are based on case studies addressing specific substances and effects as well as the general use of tools, criteria, and methods. The reviews include aspects related to human health, including the occupational setting, and the environment.

Currently addressed effects are: Endocrine Disruption, Skin sensitization, Genotoxicity and carcinogenicity, and Developmental neurotoxicity

Currently addressed substances/ groups of substances are: Biocides, plant protection products, PFAS, BPA/BPA alternatives/BPA analogues/Bisphenols, phthalates, endocrine disrupting compounds, mixtures, food contact material, cosmetics, PBT/vPvB

Currently addressed tools, criteria, and methods are: risk-based decision benchmarks, methods for evaluating the effectiveness of risk assessment for reducing risk, quantitative expressions of uncertainty, chemical data gap

filling approaches, protection of ecosystems, secondary poisoning, occupational exposures to reproductive and developmental toxicants, and workplace chemical risk assessment.

Do you have additional suggestions of aspects related to the effectiveness of risk assessment methodologies, including potential inconsistencies and/ or harmonization needs, to be reviewed for the years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/ policy need for every suggestion

Task 6.4: Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Task 6.4 aims to transpose scientific results to regulatory feasible and workable risk assessment methodologies. This task will support regulatory processes for reducing risks to humans and the environment by developing results to support the development of guidance documents and/or recommendations. In the first period they have developed activities around four regulatory important areas. 1) Developing risk assessment and management methods for chemical mixtures (across regulatory frameworks) 2) Facilitating the regulatory acceptance and use of new methods (e.g criteria for the use of NAMs) 3) Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy (including methods to improve enforcement of chemicals legislation) 4) Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity (starting initially with plant protection products)

Do you have suggestions of additional areas where activities should be developed under Task 6.4 for the years 4 to 7 of PARC?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion (you can add up to 3 suggestions, start with the high priority one)
 - Kindly explain the regulatory/ policy need for every suggestion

Under this WP (WP6), do you identify issues you would like to raise that are not covered by the current questions?

Workpackages 7 – 8 and 9

WP 7 'FAIR data' ensures that data and associated information are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The work is articulated in the following three tasks:

- **Task 7.1** 'PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and Data Management Plan (DMP)' providing the framework (guiding principles, data policy, framework DMP) and setting up specific methods and tools and guidance to FAIRify data and facilitate data reuse in the R&I WPs and in regulatory agencies.
- **Task 7.2** 'Data libraries' where data will be made FAIR at the source whenever possible, described by FAIR metadata, and associated with a persistent identifier.
- **Task 7.3** 'Innovative analyses' introducing innovative analytical approaches to maximise use and insights from increasing amounts of open and FAIR data for risk assessment.

Do you have any suggestions to consider for this WP or its tasks over the next years of PARC (years 4 to 7)?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion: Open text

WP 8 'Concepts and toolboxes' supports the development and consolidation of new concepts and tools that address key challenges of the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. The work is articulated in the following three tasks:

- **Task 8.1** 'Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)' supporting the operationalisation of the SSbD criteria and methodology developed by the EC by gathering feedback from various stakeholders, including industry, on its operational applicability, and by developing and testing a toolbox geared to support the implementation of SSbD by the various users.
- **Task 8.2** 'Scientific and technical basis for an early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks' feeding the EC's EW and action system, announced under the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability.
- **Task 8.3** 'Integrative models' aiming to place the models developed and the data that will be collected and generated within PARC in an overarching and harmonised framework and to implement this in a functional and open PARC computational tool network infrastructure, including links to the SSbD toolbox and models from other projects.

Do you have any suggestions to consider for this WP or its tasks over the next years of PARC (years 4 to 7)?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion: Open text

WP 9 'Building infrastructural and human Capacities' aims to facilitate the establishment and maintenance of the capacities needed to address current, emerging, and novel challenges in chemical hazard, exposure, and risk assessment. The work is articulated in the following four tasks:

- **Task 9.1** 'Laboratory networking' based on existing well-established laboratory networks, a task aiming to expand laboratory capacities.
- **Task 9.2** 'Building exposure monitoring capacities' mapping environmental (air, water, sediment, soil, biota), drinking water, food and feed monitoring networks in both the regulatory and research areas, biomonitoring efforts and human cohorts, to identify the gaps and opportunities for future development and/or alignment.
- **Task 9.3** 'Joint activities – harmonisation' aiming to harmonise laboratory related Quality Assurance /Quality Control across application, technique and chemical domains by implementing joint activities.
- **Task 9.4** 'Training' setting up a training network for both PARC members, risk assessors and managers.

Do you have any suggestions to consider for this WP or its tasks over the next years of PARC (years 4 to 7)?

- No
- Yes
 - Please add your suggestion: Open text

End of survey: Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey. Your responses will contribute to the mapping of needs and the results will be presented to you later.